

RHEOLOGY AS A RAPID METHOD FOR SIMPLE AND PRECISE DETERMINATION OF THE PERCOLATION THRESHOLD IN SHORT-FIBER POLYMERIC BIOCOMPOSITES: INSIGHTS INTO SUSTAINABLE MATERIAL DESIGN

Giovanni Filippone¹, Lucia Gioiella¹ and Libera Vitiello¹

¹Dipartimento di Ingegneria Chimica, dei Materiali e della Produzione Industriale, Università di Napoli Federico II
Piazzale Tecchio 80, 80125 Napoli, Italy
Email: gfilippo@unina.it

¹Dipartimento di Ingegneria Chimica, dei Materiali e della Produzione Industriale, Università di Napoli Federico II
Piazzale Tecchio 80, 80125 Napoli, Italy
Email: lucia.gioiella@unina.it

¹Dipartimento di Ingegneria Chimica, dei Materiali e della Produzione Industriale, Università di Napoli Federico II
Piazzale Tecchio 80, 80125 Napoli, Italy
Email: libera.vitiello@unina.it

Keywords: Polymer-matrix composites; Thermoplastic resins; Discontinuous reinforcement; Rheological properties; Environmental degradation

ABSTRACT

The determination of the percolation threshold (Φ_c) in particulate and short-fiber composites is essential for understanding mechanical behavior, transport properties, and degradation, especially in biocomposites with hydrolysable matrices. In such systems, percolating fiber networks promote water and degradation agent penetration, potentially accelerating biodegradation. Conventional methods to determine Φ_c (e.g. theoretical models or conductivity-based techniques) are unsuitable for biocomposites containing non-conductive, variable natural fibers. Here we summarize the results of two studies in which (i) a simple rheological protocol is proposed to accurately determine Φ_c in poly(lactic acid) biocomposites reinforced with short hemp or kenaf fibers, and (ii) the relevance of Φ_c for biodegradation purposes is thoroughly examined for the hemp-based composites.

Regarding the first point, the proposed method for the assessment of Φ_c relies on the linear viscoelastic “two-phase model” originally developed for nanocomposites but general enough to be extended to microcomposites despite the non-Brownian nature of microfibers. Rheological estimates of Φ_c were compared with values obtained via dielectric spectroscopy, which is a more complex and time-consuming method requiring water equilibration of the samples over several weeks. Regarding the second point, changes in molecular weight under two environmental conditions (water and mature compost) were studied in hemp-based composites below and above Φ_c . The results highlighted non-linear behavior in relation to filler content and showed contrasting degradation patterns between aqueous and soil-like media due to the effect of the crystallinity forming during degradation.

Overall, besides providing valuable guidance for the development of environmentally sustainable PLA-based materials with improved end-of-life performance, this study demonstrates that rheological analysis is a fast, accurate, and effective method to determine Φ_c , even in highly inhomogeneous and anisotropic materials like natural fiber biocomposites. Compared to other experimental techniques (e.g. dielectric spectroscopy), rheology offers shorter testing times and easier sample preparation, making it a promising standard method for characterizing percolation behavior in sustainable, fiber-reinforced biocomposites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Biodegradable polymer composites reinforced with natural fibers have attracted growing interest due to their eco-friendly nature and potential to replace conventional plastics. Among them, polylactic acid (PLA) is a widely used bio-based polyester derived from renewable sources such as corn starch or sugarcane. However, PLA biodegradation in natural environments can be unacceptably slow. This process involves abiotic hydrolysis of ester bonds followed by microbial assimilation of the resulting low-molecular-weight fragments. Since only chains with a molecular weight below 10–20 kDa can be mineralized by microorganisms, the rate-limiting step is the initial hydrolytic cleavage.

One strategy to accelerate PLA degradation is incorporating lignocellulosic fillers, which promote water diffusion through their hygroscopic hemicellulose content. Their swelling in moist environments can also induce matrix-filler debonding, creating capillaries that enhance water ingress. However, the overall impact of natural fibers on PLA degradation is complex and influenced by filler properties such as chemical composition, geometry, and content. In particular, the fiber volume fraction plays a crucial role, especially when it exceeds the percolation threshold (Φ_c). The latter is the critical point at which fibers form a continuous network that facilitates the transport of water and pro-degradative agents into the composite's core.

Beyond biodegradation, the identification of Φ_c is fundamental due to the abrupt changes it causes in key material properties, such as mechanical strength, rheological behavior, and diffusivity. Nevertheless, accurately determining Φ_c in green composites is challenging. Theoretical models often rely on unrealistic assumptions, while many experimental techniques are unsuitable due to the non-conductive and variable nature of natural fibers.

In this context, we present the results of two studies [1, 2] carried out on PLA-based composites filled with short fibers from hemp and kenaf, focusing on how fiber content and morphology affect degradation and percolation behavior. Two complementary experimental techniques—dielectric spectroscopy and rheological analysis—were used to identify Φ_c . While dielectric spectroscopy requires lengthy water equilibration, rheology offers a faster, simpler, and equally accurate alternative. By applying a linear viscoelastic two-phase model originally developed for nanocomposites, we isolated the fiber contribution and precisely determined Φ_c , which was around 10% for hemp and 20% for kenaf. Moreover, degradation kinetics in water and compost environments were monitored for the hemp-based composites to highlight the relevance of Φ_c for biodegradation purposes. Our results indicate that filler content has non-monotonic effects, with significant differences between conditions. These findings underline the importance of understanding the interplay between percolation, crystallinity, and filler structure to design more sustainable PLA-based materials with controlled end-of-life behavior.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

PLA pellets (Luminy® LX175, density: 1.24 g cm⁻³, MFI: 6 g/10 min at 210 °C/2.16 kg) were obtained from Corbion. Hemp shives and kenaf bast fibers were sourced from Equilibrium S.r.l. (Nibionno, Italy) and Kenaf Eco Fibers Italia (Guastalla, Italy), respectively. Prior to compounding, fibers were ground using a Retsch cutting mill with a 0.25 mm sieve. Images of the fibers before and after milling (Fig. 1) show a mix of micrometer-scale fibers and finer debris, likely generated during grinding. The ground fibers used in our composites can be assimilated to short, capped cylinders. The hemp fibers are slightly shorter than the kenaf ones (volume average length: 376±181 μm for hemp, 461±213 μm for kenaf) [1]. The distribution of the aspect ratio (length-to-diameter ratio) of the fibers after milling is also shown in Fig. 1.

2.2. Melt Compounding and Sample Preparation

PLA and fibers were compounded using a Brabender Pantograph EC batch mixer. Samples were prepared at fiber volume fractions (Φ) of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, and 35%. Prior to mixing, PLA pellets were vacuum-dried at 85 °C overnight, and fibers were conditioned at 25°C and 80% relative humidity. Compounding was carried out at 180 °C and 60 rpm for 6 min. The mixture was then dried again at 85°C under vacuum and compression molded into 100×100×3 mm³ plates using a Lab Tech Engineering hydraulic press. Molding involved a preheating phase at 180°C without pressure (5 min), compression at ~150 bar (4 min), and cooling under pressure to room temperature. The molded plates were then cut

into 30×30×3 mm³ specimens for rheological tests. Regarding the samples for the degradation tests in water and soil, the material, sandwiched between two Teflon sheets, was placed in the mold preheated at 180°C and softened for 5 minutes without pressure. Then the pressure was increased to ~15 MPa and kept constant for 4 min. Finally, the mold was cooled to ~40°C under constant pressure. The resulting plates were cut into rectangular specimens (30×10×3 mm³) using a circular saw.

Figure 1: Upper row: hemp (a–c) and kenaf (a'–c') fibers before (a, a') and after (b, b', c, c') grinding. Lower row: distribution of the aspect ratio (AR; length-to-diameter ratio) of the fibers. Images taken from [1].

2.3. Characterization Techniques

Fiber size and aspect ratio were determined via image analysis from optical micrographs obtained with an Olympus BX53M microscope. Approximately 100 particles were analyzed per fiber type. For improved visualization, fibers were suspended in diluted poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) solution before deposition on glass slides.

Sample microstructure was examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Leica 420, Wetzlar, Germany). Samples were cryo-fractured at ca. -80°C and gold-coated before imaging.

Rheological measurements were conducted on a TA Instruments AR-G2 rheometer with parallel plate geometry (25 mm diameter). Specimens were dried at 80 °C under vacuum before testing. All tests were performed using a 2 mm plate gap, with samples taken from consistent positions on the plates to minimize orientation effects from compression molding. Small-amplitude oscillatory shear (SAOS) tests were conducted at 180 °C in nitrogen. The elastic (G') and viscous (G'') moduli were collected in a frequency range between $\omega=0.06$ and $\omega=600$ rad/s. Strain amplitudes were set between 0.2% and 2%, ensuring linear viscoelastic behavior and reliable stress measurements.

For the degradation tests in water, the specimens were immersed in test tubes containing 50 mL of water (pH≈7.5) and kept at 45°C with gentle stirring in a shaking incubator (Bormarc Shaker SKI 4). Before subsequent characterization, the samples were collected at fixed time intervals and carefully dried until reaching a constant weight. The specimens for the degradation tests in soil were buried in mature green compost (water holding capacity 80%, moisture content 55%, pH=6.6) and kept in an incubator (Bormarc Shaker SKI 4) at 55°C and 20% RH. The samples were collected at fixed times and subjected to the following analyses.

Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) was performed with a Waters 590 chromatographic system equipped with HSPgel HR3 and HR4 columns and a refractive index detector. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was used as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min. The weight-average molecular weight (M_w) and the polydispersity index (M_w/M_n) were determined based on a calibration curve generated with polystyrene standards ranging from 0.370 to 100 kg/mol.

3 RESULTS

3.1. Assessment of the percolation threshold – The two-phase model

Unlike nanoparticles, which undergo Brownian motion even in highly viscous polymer melts and tend to form fractal aggregates that percolate at very low filler loadings ($\Phi_c \sim 1\%$), the fibers employed in this study are too big to exhibit Brownian behavior. In similar cases, percolation theory can be applied to estimate Φ_c by using the concept of excluded volume, V_{ex} , defined as the region around a filler particle within which the center of another particle cannot enter [3]. However, theoretical calculations suffer from the wideness of the aspect ratio distribution, which reflects in wide ranges of possible Φ_c . Further uncertainty stems from the variability of the orientation of the fibers, which affects V_{ex} . As a result, the Φ_c for the hemp fibers was estimated to range between 5.2 vol.% (perpendicular orientation) and 20.8 vol.% (parallel orientation). The range of Φ_c for the kenaf fibers was 4.3-17.2 vol.% (parallel).

To assess the values of Φ_c with much higher accuracy, experimental methods must be used. Unfortunately, when dealing with very flexible and non-conductive natural fibers dispersed in viscoelastic polymer matrices, the experimental detection of Φ_c is anything but simple. Here we propose to resort to rheology, which is a well-established characterization technique in the field of polymeric materials. In particular, we exploit the prediction ability of a simple two-phase model that we derived to describe the linear viscoelasticity of polymer nanocomposites [4, 5, 6]. Since the two-phase model only works for samples at $\Phi > \Phi_c$, and being the $G'(\omega)$ curves of these samples scalable on a single master curve by means of only two shift factors with a precise physical meaning, the Φ_c can be easily computed. In brief, the vertical shift factors for the building of the master curve represent the precise values of the elasticity of the networks of nanoparticles, G'_0 . The percolation theory predicts that the latter scale with the volume fraction as $G'_0 \sim (\Phi - \Phi_c)^v$, where v is a critical exponent that depends on the stress bearing mechanism. Fitting this law to the experimental values of the vertical shift factors for the building of the master curve eventually returns the Φ_c of the system. This simple procedure is made robust because of the deterministic feature of the shift factors, which makes the scaling of a G' curve of a sample at $\Phi < \Phi_c$ not possible.

When trying to extend such an approach to natural fibers, many differences emerge (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: differences between nano- and microcomposites. The relationship between wall-to-wall interparticle distance h and particle volume fraction Φ is shown on the left-hand side.

The non-Brownian feature of micron-sized particles prevents them from moving and rearranging in the host medium due to thermal energy, eventually flocculating in the host matrix at very low particle volume fractions. Percolation at low Φ is also disfavored by the relatively long wall-to-wall distance (h) between contiguous particles. Nonetheless, the basic principle underlying the two-phase model, i.e. the coexistence of two well-distinct populations of dynamical species (the particle network and the host polymer matrix) remain valid. As a result, we expect that the previous procedure to compute Φ_c can be used also for the biocomposites under investigation.

The master curves built for the hemp- and kenaf-based composites are shown in Figure 3.a and b. The critical scaling of the network elasticity with $\Phi - \Phi_c$ is reported in Figure 3.c.

Figure 3: a and b) Master curves of G' for hemp- (a) and kenaf-based composites (b) at $\Phi \geq 15$ vol% and $\Phi \geq 20$ vol%, respectively. The inserts show the G' curves of samples at different Φ before the scaling. c) Critical scaling of the network elasticity for hemp- (circles) and kenaf-based (triangles) composites. The dashed lines are the best fitting curves. $R^2=0.9780$ (hemp) and 0.9311 (kenaf). Images readapted from [1].

The above procedure led to $\Phi_c=10.1$ and 19.5 vol% for the hemp- and kenaf-based composite, respectively. These values were confirmed by means of broadband dielectric spectroscopy, which was carried out by using an ARES rheometer equipped with a dielectric analysis tool connected to an Agilent E4980A LCR meter. This method exploits the high sensitivity of the complex permittivity (ϵ^*) to the water contained in the fibers, which makes it possible to correlate Φ_c to a discontinuity in the (di)electric response [7, 8, 9]. In this way we obtained $\Phi_c=10.1$ and 18.5 vol% for the hemp- and kenaf-based composite, in excellent agreement with the linear viscoelasticity results. It is worth mentioning that a much more laborious and time-consuming procedure was needed in the case of dielectric tests because of the need of a very long (ca. 1 month) conditioning step before the measurements [1].

3.2. Effect of the percolation threshold of the degradation kinetics of PLA-hemp biocomposites

Once the percolation threshold has been estimated with accuracy, its role in dictating the degradation kinetics of hydrolysable matrices was investigated. The results of degradation tests in freshwater and mature compost are summarized in Table 1, where the evolution of M_w and M_n assessed by SEC is reported as a function of time for samples at different Φ .

After 50 days of immersion in freshwater, a clear inverse relationship emerges between fiber content and molecular weight: as the fiber loading increases, M_w decreases. This means that the formulation with the highest fiber fraction shows the most pronounced reduction in molecular weight (over 40%). Interestingly, even though the fiber network becomes more interconnected beyond the percolation threshold ($\Phi_c=10.1\%$), no abrupt changes in the degradation trend are observed.

The PLA exhibits a significantly faster degradation rate in soil, which is expected due to the elevated temperature and microbial activity typical of composting conditions. Regarding the influence of fibers, an acceleration in the degradation kinetics is observed after 10 days. An effect of the percolation threshold is noticed, even if a substantial acceleration is only observed from $\Phi=15\text{vol}\%$, that is well above Φ_c . What is more interesting is that the trend reverses at longer burial times, when the fibers surprisingly appear to inhibit degradation.

	Φ [vol.%]	0	5	10	15	20	25	30
as prepared samples (reference)	M_w [kDa]	113.9		110.3		100.8		113.6
	M_w/M_n	1.6		1.4		1.6		1.5
after 50 days in freshwater	M_w [kDa]	85.8	84.8	80.6	79.5	79.1	76.5	69.4
	M_w/M_n	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.6
after 10 days in soil	M_w [kDa]	83.2	89.4	84.3	78.7	73.1	67.4	65.6
	M_w/M_n	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.7	1.8	1.8
after 20 days in soil	M_w [kDa]	24.8	41	53.6	56.3	71.8	63.4	70.3
	M_w/M_n	1.8	1.8	1.7	1.7	1.5	1.7	1.6

Table 1: Average molecular weight and polydispersity indices of PLA composites in different environments.

The reduction in molecular weight is known to be autocatalytic, with the degradation process accelerating once the molecular weight drops below a critical threshold (M_c), beyond which oligomeric chains begin to solubilize into the surrounding medium [10]. According to Stloukal *et al.*, this threshold is approximately 20 kDa for PLA in soil [11]. As shown in Table 1, pure PLA reaches this value within around 20 days, whereas composites with increasing fiber content require more time. Nonetheless, degradation remains relatively fast, with composites approaching M_c between 20 and 40 days. After 40 days, size exclusion chromatography (SEC) reveals the presence of three distinct chain populations: low (~ 2 kDa), intermediate (~ 5 kDa), and high (> 10 kDa) molecular weights. It is important to note that SEC measurements at extended burial times may underestimate degradation due to the loss of water-soluble oligomers, which are no longer present in the solid phase. Despite this limitation, the data indicate that fiber incorporation slows degradation, particularly at higher loadings. To understand this behavior, which contrasts with observations in freshwater, one must consider the relationship between molecular weight evolution and the crystallinity of the samples during composting. A thorough DSC characterization (DSC Q2000, TA Instruments) demonstrated that the reduced degradation rate observed in composites with high Φ can be attributed to the protective influence of fiber-induced crystallinity, which hinders water penetration and shields the amorphous regions from hydrolytic attack [2]. In essence, within mature compost, the fibers initially facilitate water uptake during the early stages of burial. This effect, which seems to be favored at fiber contents well above Φ_c , vanishes over time. As burial progresses, the crystallinity promoted by the fibers becomes dominant, ultimately slowing down the overall degradation process.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The percolation threshold of PLA-based composites reinforced with short hemp shives or kenaf bast fibers (average length $< 500 \mu\text{m}$) was evaluated by applying and validating a model originally conceived to depict the linear viscoelasticity of polymer nanocomposites. Despite the substantial differences with biocomposites, the physics underlying the two-phase model keeps working, the only difference being the higher filler contents needed for percolation in this class of composites based on micron-sized reinforcing fibers. The two-phase model led to Φ_c values of ~ 10.1 vol% for hemp and 19.5 vol% for kenaf composites. Dielectric spectroscopy supported these findings, though it required more complex sample preparation. Regarding the relevance of the percolation threshold on the degradation kinetics, the impact of short hemp fibers on PLA degradation in freshwater and mature compost was evaluated using SEC analyses, with fiber content ranging from 5 to 30 vol%, surpassing the percolation threshold. A contrasting behavior was observed: in freshwater, fibers accelerated degradation by promoting hydrolysis and enabling water infiltration, even affecting crystalline regions. In compost, degradation

was generally faster due to the biotic environment and higher temperature (~55 °C). While fibers initially enhanced hydrolysis and surface erosion, over time, the fiber-induced crystallinity slowed PLA degradation compared to the neat polymer. Additionally, the fibers slightly improved the flexural modulus of the composites, potentially enabling material savings and enhancing sustainability throughout their life cycle.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

G.F. acknowledges financial support under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), Mission 4, Component 2, Investment 1.1, Call for tender No. 104 published on 02.02.2022 by the Italian Ministry of University and Research (MUR), funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU-Project Title “Untapping the potential of GREEN COmposites by combining performance and environmental sustainability - GREENCO”, grant number 20223LWKTC, grant assignment decree No. 966 adopted on 30/06/2023 by MUR.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Vitiello, M. Salzano de Luna, V. Ambrogi and G. Filippone, A simple rheological method for the experimental assessment of the fiber percolation threshold in short fiber biocomposites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **245**, 2024, p. 110345 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2023.110345](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2023.110345))
- [2] L. Vitiello, S. C. Carroccio, V. Ambrogi, E. Podda, G. Filippone and M. Salzano de Luna, Degradation kinetics of PLA/hemp biocomposites: Tradeoff between nucleating action and pro-hydrolytic effect of natural fibers, *Composites Science and Technology*, **257**, 2024, p. 110345 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2024.110806](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2024.110806))
- [3] I. Balberg, C. H. Anderson, S. Alexander and N. Wagner, Excluded volume and its relation to the onset of percolation. *Physical review B*, **30**, 1984, p. 3933 (doi: 10.1103/PhysRevB.30.3933).
- [4] G. Filippone, G. Romeo and D. Acierno, Viscoelasticity and structure of polystyrene/fumed silica nanocomposites: filler network and hydrodynamic contributions. *Langmuir*, **26**, 2010, pp. 2714-2720. (doi: [10.1021/la902755r](https://doi.org/10.1021/la902755r))
- [5] G. Filippone, M. Salzano de Luna, D. Acierno and P. Russo, Elasticity and structure of weak graphite nanoplatelet (GNP) networks in polymer matrices through viscoelastic analyses, *Polymer*, **53**, 2012, pp. 2699-2704. (doi: [10.1016/j.polymer.2012.04.037](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymer.2012.04.037))
- [6] G. Capuano, G. Filippone, G. Romeo and D. Acierno, Universal Features of the Melt Elasticity of Interacting Polymer Nanocomposites, *Langmuir*, **28**, 2012, pp. 5458-5463. (doi: [10.1021/la205105m](https://doi.org/10.1021/la205105m))
- [7] A. N. Fraga, E. Frullloni, O. De la Osa, J. M. Kenny and A. Vázquez, Relationship between water absorption and dielectric behaviour of natural fibre composite materials. *Polymer testing*, **25(2)**, 2006, pp. 181-187 (doi: [10.1016/j.polymertesting.2005.11.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2005.11.002))
- [8] E. Jayamani, S. Hamdan, M.R. Rahman and M. K. B. Bakri, Comparative study of dielectric properties of hybrid natural fiber composites. *Procedia Engineering*, **97**, 2014, pp. 536-544 (doi: [10.1016/j.proeng.2014.12.280](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2014.12.280))
- [9] W. Wang, M. Sainand P. A. Cooper, Study of moisture absorption in natural fiber plastic composites. *Composites science and technology*, **66**, 2006, pp. 379-386 (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.07.027](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.07.027))
- [10] M. Karamanlioglu, R. Preziosi and G. D. Robson, Abiotic and biotic environmental degradation of the bioplastic polymer poly (lactic acid): A review. *Polymer Degradation and stability*, **137**, 2017, pp. 122-130 (doi: [10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2017.01.0](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2017.01.0))
- [11] P. Stloukal, S. Pekařová, A. Kalendova, H. Mattausch, S. Laske, C. Holzer, L. Chitu, S. Bodner, G. Maier, M. Slouf and M. Koutny, Kinetics and mechanism of the biodegradation of PLA/clay nanocomposites during thermophilic phase of composting process. *Waste Management*, **42**, 2015, pp. 31-40 (doi: [10.1016/j.wasman.2015.04.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2015.04.006))